

**ANALYSIS OF INDEPENDENT LEARNING TECHNOLOGY IN
TEACHING STUDENTS FOREIGN LANGUAGE**

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Annotation: In this article, successful information from each of the modern methods of teaching a foreign language, independent learning technologies is analyzed. Allows students to adjust any technology according to the structure, functions, content, goals and objectives of teaching in a specific group of students.

Key words: Independent educational technology, communication method, essay, essay-reflection, discussion, dialogue, pedagogical system.

Аннотация: В данной статье анализируются успешные сведения каждой из современных методик обучения иностранному языку, самостоятельных образовательных технологий. Позволяет учащимся корректировать любую технологию в соответствии со структурой, функциями, содержанием, целями и задачами обучения в конкретной группе учащихся.

Ключевые слова: Самостоятельная образовательная технология, метод общения, эссе, эссе-размышление, дискуссия, диалог, педагогическая система.

Language is the most important means of communication, without which the existence and development of human society is impossible. Today, changes in social relations and means of communication (use of new information technologies) require increasing the communicative competence of students, improving their philological preparation, exchanging ideas in various situations during interaction with them. Other communication participants, at the same time, the correct use of the system of language and speech norms and the selection of communicative behavior adequate to the actual communication situation. In other words, the main goal of a foreign language is the formation of communicative competence, that is, the ability to carry out interpersonal and intercultural communication in a foreign language with native speakers. The educational aspect is an integral part of the educational process, therefore, all educational technologies ensure the education of the necessary qualities of a mature person in students. Materials and methods: modern educational technologies used for the formation of the student's communicative competence in a foreign language are the most effective for creating an educational environment that ensures personal interaction of all participants of the educational process. It is clear that the use of any teaching technology, no matter how perfect it is, cannot create the most effective conditions for revealing and developing the abilities of students, for creative research of the teacher. The search for new pedagogical technologies is associated with the lack of positive motivation to learn a foreign language in some students. Positive motivation is not enough, and sometimes there is none, because when learning a

foreign language, they face great difficulties and do not master the material due to their psychological characteristics. The main goal of the independent education method is to give students the opportunity to learn independently in the process of solving practical issues or problems that require the integration of knowledge from different disciplines. If we talk about this method as a pedagogical technology, then this technology implies a set of research, research, problem-solving methods of a creative nature. Internally, the role of project developer, coordinator, expert, consultant is defined for the teacher. This technology develops students' creativity, imagination and interests. Creative and intellectual potential of students is revealed during the preparation of independent tasks. The project method teaches research, teamwork, discussion, and problem solving. Life in modern society requires students to develop important cognitive skills such as developing their own thoughts, understanding experience, building a chain of evidence, and expressing their thoughts clearly and convincingly.

The technique of developing independent thinking involves asking students questions and understanding the problem to be solved. Critical thinking has an individual independent character, everyone creates their own ideas, forms their own assessments and beliefs independently of others, finds a solution to the problem and supports it with reasonable, reasonable and reliable evidence. Independent thinking is social because every thought is tested and shared with others. The student's active life position is especially evident when comparing previously existing knowledge and concepts with newly acquired knowledge. There are various forms of work that ensure the development of independent thinking of students: essay, essay-reflection, discussion, dialogue, role-playing, etc. In order to develop intercultural communication skills, it is important to give

students a thorough knowledge of the culture, customs and traditions of the English-speaking country, so that students can have an objective view and consciously choose their own communication style. they get Modeling situations of communication between cultures in English classes allows students to compare the lifestyle characteristics of people in our country and in the countries of the studied language, helps them better understand the culture of our country and develops the ability to express it. through English. Such an approach is possible only when using real teaching tools. To find that information and communication technologies are increasingly used in the organization of the educational process, to allow effective consideration of all possible aspects (from linguistics to cultural studies), to improve the speech activity of a foreign language. Their use improves students' linguistic and intercultural competencies. to improve, to form the culture of communication in the electronic environment, to increase the information culture in general, as well as the computer helps to develop skills: search, processing, transfer, systematization. presentation of data and results of research activities by students.

Interactive exercises and tasks performed by students form the basis of interactive approaches. The main difference between independent exercises and regular exercises is that they are aimed not only at strengthening the learned material, but also at learning new ones.

Conclusion part: New independent education learning and strengthening the material (interactive lecture, working with visual aids, video and audio materials, "student as a teacher", "everyone teaches everyone").

Under the discussion of complex and controversial issues and problems, creative tasks we understand such educational tasks that require students not to simply repeat information, but creativity, because the tasks contain a more or less element of uncertainty and, as a rule, has several approaches. The creative task is the content and basis of any interactive. A creative task (especially practical and close to the student's life) gives meaning to learning, motivates students. The uncertainty of the answer and the ability to find your "correct" solution based on your personal experience and the experience of your colleague, friend will allow you to create a basis for cooperation, joint education, communication of all participants.

Working in small groups is an integral part of many interactive methods, such as mosaics, discussions, public hearings, almost all types of simulation, etc. Make sure students have the necessary knowledge and skills to complete the group assignment. The lack of knowledge will soon make itself felt - students will not try to complete the task. You should try to make your instructions as specific as possible. It is unlikely that the group will be able to grasp more than one or two, even very specific, instructions at a time, so the instructions should be written on the board or cards. Give the group enough time to complete the task. When it comes to the practical application of technologies, it is not necessary to use one technology at all.

The best way was to combine several educational technologies, combining their best aspects. As we are engaged in the integration of modern educational technologies in the process of teaching a foreign language to form a student's independent education, it is necessary to carefully study the innovative ideas of modern Russian and foreign teachers for several years. To reveal the subjective

experience of the student, to form educational work methods that are personally important for him, to educate moral ideals, to develop critical thinking, it is concluded that it is this pedagogical system that promotes adequate assessment and self-management.

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